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Impact of Social Media on Politics and Peacebuilding in Nigeria's Democracy

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Abstract

Nigeria as a country, continues to witness unprecedented escalation of violence ranging from deadly ethno-religious clashes to genocidal killings particularly in the Middle Belt, something media pundits often profile as herder-farmer conflicts. Government and stakeholders, have engendered various measures for social engagement aimed at curbing the menace, promoting security and sustainable peace. Connected internet technologies have revolutionized how the Nigerian society interacts in its deliberative engagements for democracy, social wellbeing and peaceful coexistence. In the last decade, technology-driven methods of information dissemination and mass mobilization in Nigeria have become acutely pronounced. The explosive impact of the social media has overwhelmed the traditional channels of social influencers and opinion moulders in Nigerian politics and democratic governance. This study investigates the impact of social media on politics and peacebuilding in Nigeria's democracy and highlights how the new media can have direct impact on political struggle, responsive governance and conflict resolution. The theoretical framework of the study is anchored on social network theory. The study combines the qualitative and historical

approaches to research based on document investigation. Information collated from scholarly publications, which provide vital insights into wide-ranging angles of the study, is carefully sifted and analyzed. The study objectively presents its finding, namely that social media is a double-edged sword; it can be deployed to promote peacebuilding, but it can also instigate and escalate conflicts. The paper concludes that by collaborative efforts, Nigeria can mitigate the abuse of social media, deepen democracy and promote peacebuilding. It recommends a balanced approach to content regulation which promotes freedom of expression but ends the culture of impunity in Nigeria.

Keywords: Social Media, Democracy, Politics, Peacebuilding

Introduction

Communication undoubtedly plays a strategic role in entrenching democracy and engendering peacebuilding. The emergence of social media with its user-friendly technologies has revolutionized political engagement and means of interaction between governments and the governed. Social media has become a phenomenal avenue for information dissemination, political sensitization, public mobilization and social activism whether in the organized private sector or public institutions. Aondover, Okuneye and Onyejelem (2024) assert that,

56 per cent of people worldwide are online and 45 per cent use social media, a percentage that is projected to rise over the next 20 years. Social media platforms like Facebook, WhatsApp, and Twitter to mention a few can be utilized to maintain peace, if properly used. Social media has grown in importance as a mobilizing tool in recent years because it fosters political change, social movement, and discussion. It offers fresh resources to promote communication, gather information, and analyze conflicts.

This means that with an estimated population of 200 million citizens, it should be safe to project that at least 90 million Nigerians use social media. This projection is significant because the figure is virtually at par with the over 87 million registered voters who are reported to have collected their Permanent Voter's Cards. Sulaimon (2023) of *The Punch* newspaper (23rd February, 2023) reported that the Independent National Electoral Commission announced that over 87 million registered voters had collected their Permanent Voters Cards preparatory to the 2023 general polls. Democracy is anchored on freedom of citizens to express, promote and

pursue preferred ideological viewpoints from an array of the political milieu for sorting out best public interest. In Nigeria, mass communication played an important role in the struggle for the enthronement of democracy, and still does in its survival and institutionalization. Following her independence in 1960, Nigeria has cultivated the longest period of uninterrupted democratic governance free from military incursions since May 1999.

Despite this plausible feat however, Nigeria's political dynamics and democratic governance have been remarkably stained with recurrent violence. Rival groups are at each other's jugular especially during electioneering circles, either desperately trying to acquire or hold tenaciously to power by any means whatsoever, including manipulations and violence. The emergence of the social media as an avenue for information dissemination in Nigeria has impacted enormously on social connectivity, political engagement and democratic governance. Babaleye, Ibitoye and Odorume (2020) share the view that,

The rule of law and good information management are sacrosanct to the success of any democratic government. One popular channel used by the polity to address pertinent political issues these days is the social media... citizens post messages on issues of corruption, terrorism, insurgency, economic mismanagement and poor governance which are key factors affecting society. Their contents are user generated and do not go through scrutiny of the gate keeper as is the practice in the traditional media.

It can be deduced from the foregoing that the emergence of social media platforms as means of communication and information dissemination have extended the coast of the freedom of expression and its capacity to shape public perceptions, attitudes, conduct and response to government policies. Whereas social media can help promote dialogue and understanding among peoples of diverse backgrounds, it can also stir conflicts in societies. Unlike the mainstream media, which is regulated, social media is more susceptible to technological manipulations, which can occasion violence propelling contents hence its effects on politics, governance and peacebuilding.

The impact of social media on politics and peacebuilding in Nigeria's democracy is precisely the issue this study aspires to interrogate. Proper application of the social media can enhance democracy but its misuse can stifle the growth of democracy and compromise efforts geared at

peacebuilding. The paper delves into the historical antecedents that occasioned the growth of social media and its impact on Nigeria's politics and democracy. It identifies the ways social media has led to conflict generation and possible violence in Nigeria and suggests ways social media can be deployed to promote peacebuilding and therefore deepening democracy in Nigeria. It is hoped that the paper's recommendations will enhance peacebuilding and advancement of Nigeria's thriving democracy. This paper is theoretical. It integrates elements of qualitative as well as historical research methods. The researchers believe that drawing on the strengths of both approaches will allow for deeper insights into the study. The paper places substantial reliance on secondary data with a variety of sources including published or unpublished materials, public records, textbooks, journals, newspaper articles or research works. To provide understanding of the research phenomenon, the study is theoretically grounded on the Social Network Theory.

Freeman (2004) eulogize Jacob Moreno for his "mammoth works" in developing the Social Network Theory. According to him, Moreno along with others in the 1930s pioneered a framework for understanding how relationships between individuals or groups shape social structures and influence social behavior. He further explains that the social network theory "explores with how information spreads through social connections and how social media relationships have become influential in shaping social behavior". Wenlin Liu et al (2017) provide further illumination on this theory. They elucidate that, "Social network theory focuses on the role of social relationships in transmitting information, channeling personal or media influence, and enabling attitudinal or behavioral change." They examine how relationships and connections between individuals, groups, or organizations affect behavior. According to them, information dissemination, social dynamics and interconnectivity provide insights into how social relationships can shape social behavior.

Applying the social network theory to the impact of social media on politics and peacebuilding in Nigeria's democratic governance, it could be inferred that it provides framework for understanding the how relationships between citizens influence social conduct. The theory investigates how information dissemination through social interconnectivity and social media relationships, have become influential in moulding social perceptions, attitudes and behaviour. Thus, the social network theory is best suited for

this study, this is because it would provide a credible basis for understanding how social media shapes the opinion of individual citizens or groups.

A better understanding of the impact of social influencers and opinion moulders is crucial because these have direct bearing with political engagement and the deepening of democracy in Nigeria. A deeper grasp of the influence of social media in information dissemination and therefore opinion moulding will also enhance constructive social engagement. Constructive debates by political enthusiasts on social media platforms such as Twitter, Instagram, TikTok and Facebook, will necessarily promote issue-based exchanges and this incubates credible opposition. Constructive social engagements and competitive exchange of ideas is healthy for Nigeria because it expands the frontiers of the country's democracy. A healthy democracy in turn promotes conflict resolution and peacebuilding efforts in Nigeria especially during electioneering cycles. This trajectory of the social network theory aligns with and is very consistent with the goals of this study.

Conceptual Clarifications

Four concepts are central to facilitating an objective understanding of the paper; they include Social Media, Democracy, Politics and Peacebuilding all of which significantly influence the conceptual clarification of the study.

Social Media

In defining social media, Shem, Gambo and Graham (2023), relied on Kaplan and Haenlein as well as Carr and Hayes who respectively described social media as, "groups of Internet-based applications that are founded on the ideological and technological underpinnings of Web 2.0 and that allow the creation and exchange of user-created content... Social media are internet-based channels that enable users to opportunistically interact and selectively self-present, either in real-time or asynchronously, with both broad and narrow audiences to derive value from user-generated content and the perception of interaction with others." In this study, social media is multiple interactive software such as Facebook, WhatsApp and X (Twitter) which connect people in real-time or otherwise, enabling the exchange information of interest using communications technologies.

Politics

The concept of politics entertains a gamut of definitions. Eleagu (2018) relied on popular American theorist, Harold Dwight Lasswell who said politics means, “who gets what, when and how.” Some scholars also trace the etymological roots of ‘politics’ to the Greek word *polis*, meaning everything that concerns or belongs to the *polis* or city-state. Modebadze (2010), explain that, since the city-states no longer exist, the modern form of this definition is ‘what concerns the state’. He therefore sees politics as the study of the state, its aims and purposes – the institutions by which those are going to be realized, its relations with its individual members and with other states. This paper considers politics as the deliberate individual and institutional engagements within a given polity or abroad purposed on the goal for the acquisition and utilization of state power.

Democracy

Scholars have divergent perspectives of what democracy entails. Held (2008) traces the word ‘democracy’ to its compound Greek roots ‘*Demokratia*’,

which are *demos* (people) and *kratos* (rule). Democracy means a form of government in which, in contradiction to monarchies and aristocracies, the people rule. Democracy is not a panacea for all human problems, but it offers the most compelling principle of legitimacy – the consent of the people – as the basis for social order.

Other scholars rely on the definition provided by Abraham Lincoln who in his famous Gettysburg speech delivered in November 1863 said democracy is, “The government of the people, by the people and for the people” (Becker and Raveloson, 2008). They suggest therefore, that we can say that a government comes from the people; it is exercised by the people, and for the purpose of the people’s own interests. For this study, central to the concept of democracy is the exertion or exercise of the peoples’ collective and wilful consent as the ultimate mandate which confers legitimacy on a political regime for governance within a defined polity.

Peacebuilding

Some researchers suggest that the subject of peace-building studies gained momentum rather recently. According to Frère and Wilen (2015),

peacebuilding refers to conflict prevention or resolution activities performed by either external actors such as the UN or other

international organizations, or local actors on a community level, with the common aim of establishing a sustainable peace corresponding to more than just an absence of violence.”

Gawerc (2006) stresses that, “The intention of peace-building is to create a structure of peace that is based on justice, equity, and cooperation (i.e., positive peace), thereby addressing the underlying causes of violent conflict so that they become less likely in the future.” In this paper, peacebuilding transcends the mere quelling of violence, is about identifying and tackling the underlying causative agents of conflicts and neutralizing the chances for reigniting of conflicts.

The Role of Social Media and Information Dissemination

The paper relies on available literature and discusses closely related themes such as the role of social media and information dissemination, social media and the making of democracy in Nigeria and peacebuilding in Nigerian political dispensation. It scrutinizes the previous studies and provides insights towards a responsible use of social media for peacebuilding and good governance in Nigeria. Social media has become a consequential staple for interaction, exchange of ideas and information access in the everyday lives of Nigerians. With the advancement of communication technologies and growing access to information, social media exerts profound impact in shaping social perceptions, attitudes and opinions of citizens. Oparaugo (2021) expatiates that,

Social media has become a prominent and a powerful forum for voter enlightenment, political activism and fastest means of information dissemination. Social media therefore can be used effectively to target particular voters, encourage people to exercise their franchise and to make information go viral.

However, Shola, Deji and Abiodun (2021) caution that, “despite the enormous advantages it holds, social media has also proven to be a tool for inciting electoral violence through disinformation, misinformation, hate speech and propaganda”. Other scholars align with this concern. For example, it has been decried that restraint and decorum are vanishing quickly from online spaces. In what has been described as “a brazen new media order”, liberty and expressive culture are now confused with license and capacity to insult, demean and disparage. With the social media platforms, negative comments, speculation, misinformation, half-truths,

and rumours could be spread with little or no chance of evaluating their veracity (Uzuegbunam and Omenugha, 2018).

From the foregoing, it is obvious that the social media is a double-edged sword in Nigerian politics and democratic governance, it has transformed our political engagement bringing alongside its positive and negative impacts. It can be observed that while social media has improved our political interaction, nothing suggests that our practical or virtual political engagements on social media is strictly inspired by discernible ideological standpoints. A columnist in *The Guardian* newspaper (18th January, 2021) decries that in Nigeria, it is precisely this ideological barrenness in terms of practice that mainly informs the popular collective description of politicians and political parties in Nigeria as 'same people'. The columnist believes that in this same political clime, a political ideology is often mistaken as a manifesto (Igbo, 2021).

It can be argued that political engagement in Nigeria is driven more by politics of personalities based on the ability of opposing camps to ride on the ethno-religious and socio-political sentiments of the people. Nigeria's political milieu ought to be defined by competing ideas, worldviews and principles which drive visions on how Nigeria's societal challenges can best be resolved for the common good of all citizens. Any political engagement which thrives on ethno-religious rivalries can lead to unconstructive opposition, name calling, cyberbullying, oral violence and character mutilation of real or perceived opponents. In such circumstances, at the slightest opportunity, ethno-religious battles perpetuated on social media platforms can translate into physical conflicts and violence.

Social Media and the Making of Democracy and Politics in Nigeria

Any discussion of social media and the making of democracy and politics in Nigeria should begin with the role of mass media in enthroneing and consolidating democracy in the country. The point has been emphatically stressed that, in Nigeria, the role of the media in promoting, defending and advancing democracy and good governance at various periods in the political history of the country from the colonial times has been widely documented. The press is reported to have at various times played a critical and an appreciable role to enthrone democracy or hasten the exit of anti-democratic elements and tendencies from the country's political landscape (Suleiman, 2019).

Jaja, Badey and Brown (2018) state that,

The social media has bridged the wide informational gap which existed for a long time between the government and the governed. Opportunities that social media present in deepening democracy in the country continue to abound as more and more people get online and get connected on social networks engaging with each other on various issues, affecting them and their communities. Nigeria's political parties are increasingly using non-traditional media platforms and tools to campaign and appeal to the middle class, internet-savvy, Blackberry and smartphone toting, upwardly mobile, young men and women.

However, scholars decry how the social media have in different ways negatively affected Nigeria politics and democratic governance. Researchers lament social media abuse involving such negative acts like taunting, mocking, negative labelling, intimidation, gaslighting and name calling. Several other negative behaviours that have been equally decried include such vices as issuance of threats, rumour spreading, ethnic, religious or gender-based stereotyping, misogynistic or sexually debasing comments and libel triggers. All such unacceptable conducts lead to the spread of sectional and political strife and therefore conflicts, all these pose a threat to the sustenance of democracy in Nigeria (Olojede, 2024).

Similarly, scholars have highlighted another area of concern which is considered to be a rather recent development. Uwalaka, Amadi and Enyindah (2024) state that,

'Data Boys' covertly used social media platforms to promote, rehabilitate and sustain the image of political leaders in Nigeria. Data Boys promote their political leaders by equivocation of identities, exaggerating the performance of their principals, falsifying corruption allegations against their principals' competitor and concealing the transgressions of their principals. Data Boys have been used as vehicles for covert message dissemination and other sponsored contents which could potentially go against public interest. The posture of Data Boys is inimical to public relations practice as their overtly negative and monolithic view of online influence cheapens the significance of social media influencer praxis and electioneering campaigns in Nigeria.

From the above, and considering the dangers inherent in social media abuse, it suggests that the true character content of scrupulous politicians is concealed, their performance is misrepresented, while their opponents are

smearred, demonized or even victimized. Therefore, good characters can be disillusioned away from the political landscape in which case the country is denied quality leadership in public space. This cannot be in the best interest of Nigerian politics and democratic governance.

Peacebuilding in Nigerian Political Dispensation

Scholars stressed the point that research on peacebuilding studies gained momentum rather recently (Lamidi, Olaleye and Taleat, 2022). This could explain the paucity of literature bothering on strategies for conflict resolution and peacebuilding under Nigeria's political dispensation. Lamidi, Olaleye and Taleat (2022), while focussing on conflicts spots in Kaduna communities, observe that,

Irrespective democratic or military regimes, Nigeria suffered a minimal ability for people-driven and peace-building initiatives. Many of these administrations' judgments on the location, style, and timing of a peace intervention were based on the whims and caprices of policymakers who had little understanding of the complexities involved and the interface of conflict, particularly given Nigeria's diverse character.

It can be stated that to the Nigerian citizens, especially the generations of Nigerians who experienced military rule, peacebuilding under military regimes was simply coerced through the use of military fiat rather than by consensual dialogue which addresses the root causes of violent conflicts with the view to curtailing its reoccurrence. Addressing the remote causes of violence should be considered as the key ingredient in peacebuilding because it is designed to obstruct future violence. Some scholars highlight the point that under Nigeria's democratic dispensation, peacebuilding is necessarily an all-encompassing strategy, which focusses on addressing the root causes of conflicts.

Abeeb (2020) amplifies this view when he rightly posited that,

Democracy provides all the principles, institutions and rules that make conflict resolution possible more than any other system, especially intractable social conflicts in deeply divided societies. Democracy as a system of political decision-making is in many ways a system of conflict management in which the outcomes are unknown, but the fundamental rules of the game provide a safe arena to compete. Of all the range of tools available to conflict resolution practitioners to manage intractable

conflicts, none of them is arguably more durable over the long term but risky than the creation and nurturing of democracy.

Abeeb's glowing tribute to democracy is germane especially with regards to intractable social conflicts in deeply divided societies like in the Middle Belt region of Nigeria. This paper concedes that Abeeb is absolutely correct in emphatically asserting that "more than any other system" the "creation and nurturing of democracy" provides all the principles, institutions and rules that make conflict resolution possible. It can be observed however, that some of such societies especially in northern Nigeria including Yobe State, tend to oppose democratic governance, instead they champion, even if by violence, a religious system of governance. Considering that political engagement in Nigeria can be easily inflamed by ethno-religious passions, it can be inferred that a religious system of governance will further exacerbate strife and conflicts. This will stall efforts geared at conflict resolution, mediation and peacebuilding strategies in the country.

Towards a Responsible Use of Social Media for Peacebuilding and Good Governance in Nigerian Society

As obtains in most other conflict prone societies, the exponential rise in social media usage in Nigeria has made it easily culpable for stoking fears and escalating conflicts. This makes long-lasting conflict resolution a herculean task, thus the need for a discussion which gravitates towards a responsible use of social media for peacebuilding and good governance in Nigerian society. There's need to consider how social media will promote good governance and peacebuilding in Nigerian society. Santas and Inobemhe (2021) echo the fears that,

There seems to still be genuine concerns about the way people use social media and the dangers it poses to others. It is noteworthy that despite the immense benefits derivable from social media, not everything obtainable from the platforms is favourable to all. For example, fake news, misinformation, half-truths and many vices are attributed to the freedom provided by social media platforms. Different challenges that could stand as justification for social media regulation in Nigeria include hate speech, spread of falsehood and cyberbullying.

To effectively navigate through the contours of social media misuse, a multi-pronged approach becomes viable for promoting conflict resolution and good governance, fortifying peacebuilding and lessening the propensity for

recurring conflicts in Nigeria. In the light of this, Nsude and Onwe (2017) suggest that,

The government should liaise with service providers so they can report any situation that could lead to criminal acts through their social media platforms to the government. There should be policies and legal framework to regulate the negative use of social media and the government should intensify efforts to ensure that such policies are implemented to the core, no matter who is involved.

The challenge poised by Nsude and Onwe's recommendation stems from the fear that, for far too long, many citizens have for good reasons, always held government's motive suspect. For instance, the recent efforts to ban X (formerly Twitter) by a government which rode on the wings of social media-induced campaigns to assume power, was perceived as attempting to gag social media or perpetuate media censorship (Obi, 2016). Similarly, Santas and Inobemhe (2021) express the same caution thus,

Calls to regulate social media spaces have received a backlash from Nigerians both home and abroad. The Protection from Internet Falsehood and Manipulation Bill 2019 and The Independent National Commission for the Prohibition of Hate Speech Bill 2020 before the National Assembly are seen to target free speech, and to punish social media users for being able to express themselves.

Conclusion

The place of public engagement and information dissemination in democratic governance anywhere across the globe cannot be overemphasized. Increased political participation and civic engagement can boost political consciousness, public awareness and can narrow the gap between government and the governed. Enhanced citizens' engagement can enable the people to participate more actively in the political discuss of the country thereby holding public office holders accountable. With improved access to communications technology, social media can promote peacebuilding and therefore deepen democratic governance in Nigeria but it can also instigate conflicts and incite violence. In conclusion, by collaborative efforts, Nigeria can leverage on social media to strengthen democracy, promote good governance, and enhance citizen engagement. The country can effectively mitigate the abuse of social media on the politics and governance and promote peacebuilding in the country.

Recommendations

The paper makes the following recommendations:

1. The paper aligns with the widespread concerns against harmful, abhorrent or inappropriate social media practices leading to conflicts and violence. There has to be consequences for violence mobilization, insurrectionary conduct or character mutilation, whether in the real or virtual world. As obtains in other democratic climes around the globe, the paper recommends a balanced content regulation, which on the one hand is devoid of official repression or censorship and promotes freedom of expression but on the other hand holds accountable authors of misinformation, cyberbullying and hate speech. Government can identify, categorize and legislate on precisely what constitutes social media crime. A peer review mechanism and comparative analysis of social media legislations by other emerging economies around the world, could be immense value in assisting government to assess and adapt the most suitable methods for Nigeria. Such offensive social media contents like hate speech, fake news, phonography, antisemitism, terror video contents, racial, ethnic or gender abuse and religious extremism deserve to be checkmated.
2. In the light of the above, the paper recommends that Nigerian communication technology experts should be encouraged to develop home-created software, artificial intelligence and social media applications which are sensitive to our positive culture and social values.
3. An all-inclusive-stakeholder approach involving government, tech companies, civil liberty organizations, Information and Communication Technology experts, Internet Service Providers, legal practitioners and citizens will go a long way in providing responsible and responsive oversight against the abuse of social media. Agencies such as the National Communications Commission, INEC and law enforcement agencies can collaborate with Internet Service Providers and software practitioners to stem the abuse inherent in the use social media.
4. The paper recommends that both Nigerian and international experts as well as stakeholders in peacebuilding can develop a standard strategy for social media engagement in conflict resolution

and peacebuilding. For instance, NGOs, ethno-religious, peacebuilding agencies and media enthusiasts can create forums that facilitate dialogue, debunk misinformation, counter hate speech and promote positive narratives among citizens. In such social forums, ethnic and religious minorities or marginalized groups should be encouraged to share their perspectives, this will promote inclusivity amidst diversity.

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